

Dark Personality Traits and Online Toxicity: Linking Self-Reports to Reddit Activity

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Psychological survey used in the paper “*Dark Personality Traits and Online Toxicity: Linking Self-Reports to Reddit Activity*”. Control questions are highlighted in red.

Socio-demographic questions

1. Age

2. Gender

- Female
- Male
- Nonbinary or gender diverse
- I prefer not to disclose

3. Education

- High school or less
- Some college
- College graduate or more

4. Which of the following describes best your race/ethnicity?

- Asian/Asian American
- Black/African American
- Hispanic/Latino
- White/Caucasian
- Other

5. Which of the following describes best your political affiliation?

- Democratic
- Lean Democratic
- Lean Republican
- Republican

Psychological Instruments

Dark Side of Humanity Scale (DSHS)

INSTRUCTIONS: Consider the following statements and indicate, based on the proposed scale, how much you agree with each of them.

Possible Answers:

- Not at all like me
- Mainly unlike me
- A little unlike me
- A little like me
- Mainly like me
- Very much like me

Questions:

1. It's wise to keep track of information that I can use against people.
2. What other people feel doesn't concern me.
3. I deserve to receive special treatment.
4. It gives me pleasure to see someone successful get fired.
5. It irritates me when people don't notice how good I am.
6. The only good reason I talk to others is to get information that I can use to my benefit.
7. I can be good at pretending to care about people but most of the time I really don't care.
8. I expect people to bend the rules for me.
9. I enjoy seeing people hurt.
10. I get into a temper if I don't get the recognition that I deserve.
11. It's sometimes fun to see how far I can push someone before they catch on.
12. Success is based on survival of the fittest, I am not concerned about the losers.

13. I tend to expect special favours from others.

14. Please select Mainly like me

15. I have fantasies which involve hurting other people.

16. I can get pretty angry when others disagree with me.

17. I could look people straight in the eye and it means nothing to me to lie or to cheat them.

18. I can simulate emotions like pain and hurt to make others feel sorry for me.

19. I deserve to get what I want.

20. Hurting people would be exciting.

21. I hate being criticised so much that I can't control my temper when it happens.

22. I am willing to be unethical if I believe it will help my plans succeed.

23. For me, what's right is whatever I can get away with.

24. I deserve more out of life than other people

25. I post offensive comments on social media forums just so I can take pleasure from the hurt I cause.

26. It really makes me angry when I don't get what I deserve.

27. I believe that lying is necessary to maintain a competitive advantage over others.

28. If I'm honest all the time it won't lead to the success of my objectives.

29. I don't think the rules apply to me as much as they apply to others.

30. Please select Not at all like me

31. I would hurt somebody if it meant that I would be in control.

32. I fly into a rage if somebody expects me to do tasks that are really beneath my skill level.

33. I am willing to sabotage the efforts of other people if they threaten my own goals.

34. I don't care much if what I do hurts others.

35. I expect to be treated better than average.

36. I get pleasure from mocking people in front of their friends.

37. I can get really nasty if I don't get what I want.

38. In today's world, I feel justified in doing anything I can get away with.
39. Playing by the rules sounds nice but getting what I want is more important.
40. I only associate with people of my calibre
41. I enjoy watching people in pain.
42. I will break a promise if it works to my advantage.
43. People might describe me as mean and cruel.
44. I do not waste my time hanging out with people who are beneath me.

45. What is the capital of the U.S.A.?

- Annapolis
- Atlanta
- Baton Rouge
- Charleston
- Frankfort
- Olympia
- Salem
- Springfield
- Tallahassee
- Washington, D.C.

Cyberbullying and Trolling Deviant Scale (CTDS)

INSTRUCTIONS: Please answer the following questions about yourself as honestly as you can. Remember, your responses will be kept confidential and anonymous. At no time will you need to disclose your identity, nor will we ask you to identify yourself. **For the following online activities, how often in the past 5 years have you engaged in them with someone that you know do not know?**

Possible Answers:

- Never
- Once
- 2 / 3 times
- 4 / 5 times
- 6+ times

Questions:

1. Insulted someone that you did not know in an interactive game room?
2. Used profanity or insulting language towards a stranger online (just because)?
3. Posted rude comments or lies about a stranger that you did not know online?

4. Voted at an online bashing poll saying rude or mean things about someone you did not know?

5. Posted to a guestbook saying rude or mean things about a stranger?

6. Please select Once.

7. Posted on a website or comment thread in order to make people that you did not know to make them feel uncomfortable?

8. Posted a comment on YouTube based on an opinion you didn't actually have in order to cause disturbance playing devil's advocate?

9. Visited a Facebook/website memorial page for a deceased person that you did not know and made negative comments?

10. Made a comment on social media or a website to make others mad for your own pleasure?

11. Please select 6+ times.

12. Posted comments on websites with intentions to change the direction of the conversation (go off on a tangent)?

13. Given an inappropriate or nonrelated answer to a question asking for advice in an online forum, website, or social media site to be disruptive?

14. Became a member of an online group and acted as if you were really interested in the topic of discussion, but later began opposing the beliefs of the group to be disruptive?

15. Posting ambiguous comments on a website/forum in order to cause confusion?

Social Media Usage

1. Other than Reddit, which of the following social media, if any, do you use at least once a week? [optional / multiple choice]

Facebook

Instagram

LinkedIn

- Pinterest
- Snapchat
- TikTok
- Twitter/X
- YouTube
- Other

2. On a weekly basis, how often do you consume content on social media?

- Very Frequently
- Frequently
- Occasionally
- Rarely
- Very Rarely

3. On a weekly basis, how often do you create content on social media?

- Very Frequently
- Frequently
- Occasionally
- Rarely
- Very Rarely

4. On a monthly basis, how often do you see uncivil comments/content on social media? (i.e., by using disrespectful/insulting language, profanity, or namecalling; by engaging in personal attacks; and/or by employing racist, sexist, and xenophobic terms)

- Very Frequently
- Frequently
- Occasionally
- Rarely
- Very Rarely

5. On a monthly basis, how often are you the target of uncivil comments/content on social media? (i.e., by using disrespectful/insulting language, profanity, or namecalling; by engaging in personal attacks; and/or by employing racist, sexist, and xenophobic terms)

- Very Frequently
- Frequently
- Occasionally
- Rarely
- Very Rarely

6. On a monthly basis, how often do you resort to using uncivil comments/content on social media? (i.e., by using disrespectful/insulting language, profanity, or namecalling; by engaging in personal attacks; and/or by employing racist, sexist, and xenophobic terms)

- Very Frequently
- Frequently
- Occasionally
- Rarely
- Very Rarely